

SHORT COMMUNICATION

Why Should Children Become Familiar with Nature

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ABSTRACT

Until a few years ago, the world of Iranian children was often full of movement, mobility, and experience of nature, a real world in which nature and its landmarks, including soil, water, wind, living beings and tangible trees, and not limited to virtual image frames where even the possibility of experiencing and obtaining a simple and lasting memory such as playing soil is impossible and unattainable. Today, however, the vacancy of many childish games and mischievousness can be easily felt in green and open public spaces. Today's children look more strange and alienated in the face of nature than landlords. It is a fact that Iranian children are more familiar with their country's valuable animal and plant species such as gorasay, siberian dorrena, Asian cheetah, emperor salamander and manus boro alum, and animals such as zebras, African lions and elephants, polar bears, penguins and pandas. Who is this negligence from the other side? Why do not children spend as they should and perhaps in nature? Are limited and closed apartment spaces and the preference of computer games to group uplifting physical activities our children's choice? In this paper we review the importance of acquainting children with nature, with a focus on Iran.

INTRODUCTION

The boundary of children's strangeness to nature is so great that fewer children can be caught playing dirt, playing water, playing sand, catching butterflies, chasing ants and bees, or even getting caught by a tree when climbing a tree [1-4]. The silent and overwhelmed children of the modern world, whose computer games filled their minds, are the children of the same generation who knew the game at the heart of nature and with a lot of noise [5-7]. Today's adults or yesterday's children who spent hours cooking for outdoor cooking, rocking games on the branch of a tree, catching frogs, camping outdoors, planting vegetables, entering chicken nests and roosters, riding on live animals, playing water, finding sparrow nests and slums, and 1,000 childish contraptions to play, are now the parents of children who played games in cyberspace. Prefer to any other recreation [8-10]. The undeniable fact is that our children have already not only inherited a fragile and vulnerable environment, but are even so often caught up in the virtual world that the importance of recognizing and protecting the environment doesn't make sense to them. Is it all our children's choice?

The necessity of friendship with nature for children

The reality of today's modern world is a change in lifestyle, which is of course not problematic in itself. Obviously, a lifestyle can be criticized when the effects and consequences are negatively charted [11-14]. The first warning of today's lifestyle changes on children may be sought in the latest statistics published by the world health organization: Iran is one of the seven countries with high child obesity rates. In addition, the study on more than 30,000 Iranian children shows that the prevalence of obesity and obesity among Iranian children is about 27.9% and 22.3% compared to international standards, respectively, and these figures

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are of contemplation [15-18]. According to several scientific researches, it can be stated clearly that one of the most important causes of obesity in sedentary children is lifestyle changes and moving away from natural environments [19]. This shows why Iranian children today need nature more than ever before, and at the same time, real and natural movements and struggles, not virtual voices. On the other hand, studies attest to the fact that the root of treatment for many childhood disorders and abnormalities lies in nature. The positive impact of animal therapy in the treatment of diseases such as autism, developmental abnormalities, hyperactivity disorder, conduct disorder and defiant disorder and describes it as a useful coping have been already reported [20-22].

The concept of playing in the new generation has unfortunately changed. Computerized children are likely to have a lower lifespan than their parents, and the root of this is inactivity, according to the expert [23]. Keeping children out of nature has caused a lot of behavioral disorder. The negative consequences of abstaining from physical activity and raising children in closed frameworks has been observed which refers that not touching nature in today's children is a crisis that needs to be taken seriously [24]. Most experts believe that this is the root of many chronic diseases in children such as diabetes, heart problems, asthma, shortness of breath at bedtime, vitamin d deficiency, stress and especially hyperactivity. There is no direct relationship with nature, while physical and physical activity brings major benefits such as stronger and healthier skeleton, healthier muscles, reduced obesity, and especially reduced risk of chronic and common diseases in children. Keep in mind that useful childhood environmental education is definitely an effective solution not only for nature conservation but also for enjoying and benefiting from its numerous benefits [25-29]. Research shows that many adult speeches, concerns and behaviors, even exaggerated about the past and portraying a pristine and cleaner world, can all provide children with useful information for a more realistic understanding of nature, and this is a direct and useful experience that can multiply the importance of nature conservation, especially among children [30,31].

Children's friendship with nature underlies environmental protection

Most environmental education practitioners and experts believe that so far, most efforts have been made to educate adults environmentally while in adulthood one can only be informed, but it is too late for arousal [32]. These experts believe that arousal of children can play an important role in protecting the environment, which is already extremely vulnerable and fragile and requires serious attention. The environmental education for children acts as an effective protective lever, and parents should note that they should not be in any way instructed to educate the child [33-36]. For example, if you want your child to consume less electricity and turn off the light bulbs when leaving the room, take the

time to explain why this is necessary [37]. We cannot ask our children to be environmentally friendly if we don't ourselves. One of the most effective ways for our children to respect nature and understand the need to protect the environment is to take them to nature and get help from those who specialize in this area. Environmental camps are not only interesting for children, but will change their visibility of the surrounding environment in a short time [38-40].

Studies showed that most children undergoing practical environmental education are not only more creative, motivated and academically successful than their other peers, but also more repetitively than their parents when they are in the natural arena. Children who have experienced attendance in natural schools or high-end natural environments are more physically active, more physically conscious about the diet, more creative in terms of group work, and more successful in terms of dealing and social relationships with others. The responsibility of these children to nature and all its elements is exemplary [41,42].

Children also want to know more about nature

It is reported that depriving children of green and recreational spaces, especially on the neighborhood scale, could pose a serious risk of behavioral disorders in children. These disorders include excessive anxiety (up to 40 percent in the statistical population), a disorder known as persistent impatience and grumpiness (up to 20 percent in the statistical population), a variety of behavioral disorders, and especially ADHD [43].

Many child psychologists today believe that life education classes in nature and providing children with animals are one of the solutions to encourage children not only to take more responsibility but also to avoid multiple behavioral disorders while granting them some form of controlled autonomy. All children need nature, not just those whose parents respect nature, not just those who belong to a particular social and cultural stratum and not those with special abilities and talents. Every child needs nature. Many children in today's world prefer computer games and hours of staying indoors, but is this really their choice? Have we shown them another option as parents? Our children have the right to walk in nature, ask questions and get answers. So every child needs nature and environmental education.

CONCLUSION: NATURE SCHOOLS IN IRAN

Studies show that children will be extremely sensitive and committed to the fate of nature and the environment in the future if they have a continuous and tangible experience of being in nature before they reach the age of 12. Children's age is very important in the effectiveness of environmental education, so that a proper education up to 11 or up to 12 years of age can bring positive and permanent behavior in the child, while primary school education may not be able

to be so effective. The idea of establishing nature schools in Iran has been based precisely on these priorities and necessities. The nature schools in Iran has achieved success in the field of children's education and their reconciliation with nature in the last few years. These schools try to improve their motivation to learn as much as possible while properly communicating children with nature and animals. Those involved in the implementation of these schools in Iran believe that doing various activities such as cooking firewood, building and equipping wooden painting huts, playing with animals, touring the heart of nature and various discoveries can all make children more eager to learn and understand nature and the surrounding environment. Children in these schools not only play outdoors, but even learn and gain experience in this space. Outdoor play, which often has slower beats and less planning, is an effective way to explore and explore children.

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